

Dilatometric Studies of Protonation of Some Pivalates

B. S. LARK*, T. IJIMA** and J. KOMIYAMA

Department of Chemistry, Guru Nanak Dev University,
Amritsar, India

Manuscript received 23 June 1977, revised 30 August 1980,
accepted 1 November 1980

It has been shown that tetraalkyl ammonium pivalates in solution undergo ion pair binding¹, and thus the observed volume of protonation of such salts is not only due to the reaction (1).

or to the overall reaction

where, $\text{Pi}^1 =$ pivalate ion $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{C}-\text{COO}^-$ and $\text{TAA}^+ =$ tetraalkylammonium ion, but also includes the contribution from the ion pair formation represented by the equilibrium,

with association constant

$$K_a = \frac{[\text{TAA}^+ \dots \text{Pi}^1]}{[\text{TAA}^+][\text{Pi}^1]} \quad \dots (4)$$

The degree of association (β) may be defined as the ratio of the associated moiety to the associated + unassociated salt by the expression,

$$\beta = \frac{[\text{TAA}^+ \dots \text{Pi}^1]}{[\text{Pi}^1] + [\text{TAA}^+ \dots \text{Pi}^1]} \quad \dots (5)$$

substituting for Pi^1 from equation (3),

$$\beta = \frac{K_a[\text{TAA}^+]}{1 + K_a[\text{TAA}^+]} \quad \dots (6)$$

This is expected from equilibrium (3) that on the addition of a supporting electrolyte, (i.e., TAACl), when protonation is carried out by HCl ion pair formation is enhanced resulting in further shrinkage of hydration and on protonation an increase in volume of protonation is expected.

The present work has been carried out to study the effect of supporting electrolytes on the volume of protonation of the following four systems :

* For correspondence.

** Department of Polymer Science, Tokyo Institute of Technology, O-okayama, Meguro-Ku, Tokyo, Japan.

System	Supporting electrolyte
1. Sodium pivalate (Napi)	NaCl
2. Tetramethylammonium pivalate (TMAPi)	TMACl
3. Tetraethylammonium pivalate (TEAPi)	TEACl
4. Tetrabutylammonium pivalate (TBAPi)	TBACl

Experimental

TMA and TEA chlorides (Tokyo Kasei Kogyo Co., Japan and Eastman Kodak Co., N. Y. respectively) were used as such without further purification. TBACl was prepared in the laboratory by double decomposition of TBABr with silver chloride and double recrystallisation. Tetraalkylammonium hydroxides were diluted to required concentration before use. Pivalic acid was distilled under vacuum and middle fraction was collected for further use.

Dilatometry: Circulation dilatometer introduced by Iijima *et al.*, the design and working of which are described elsewhere¹ was used.

Solutions of tetraalkylammonium pivalates were prepared by first exactly neutralising pivalic acid with corresponding TAA-OH, pH metrically. Same stock solution was used and during protonation it was taken in the lower compartment of the dilatometer (40 ml) and HCl having the same normality (0.01) was taken in the upper compartment (20 ml). Thus the same degree of neutralization (0.5) was used in all the experiments. The salt and acid solutions used, had almost the same concentration. Assuming complete neutralization the degree of neutralization was then given by the ratio of upper and lower compartment volumes of the dilatometer. Volumes of protonation have been calculated for one equivalent of HCl.

Results and Discussion

Volume of protonation (ΔV) of NaPi, TMAPi (0.014), TEAPi (0.01M) and TBAPi (0.01M) solutions in the presence of varying concentrations of corresponding supporting electrolytes were determined. The results have been plotted against total ionic strength (M) in Fig. 1. The total ionic strengths are obtained from the contribution of supporting electrolyte and of reactants and products as per suggestions of Katz and Miller². Visual extrapolation of the plot yields ΔV° for the four systems as 17.20, 17.62, 17.96 and 18.96 ml mol⁻¹.

In view of overall protonation reaction in all the four systems being the same, same value of ΔV° is expected, irrespective of the nature of the cation.

Fig. 1. Plot of volume of protonation (ΔV) and residual volume (ΔV_r) vs ionic strength.

Systematic increase observed in ΔV° values with the increasing hydrophobic character of the corresponding cation, stresses the presence of hydrophobic interaction right up to infinite dilution. Such type of interactions between the various hydrophobic parts of polyelectrolytes have been shown to be existing down to very low concentrations by Nakagawa⁴ and Kauzmann⁵.

ΔV values have been fitted by the method of least squares to the equation

$$\Delta V = \Delta V^\circ + S \sqrt{M} + bM \quad \dots (7)$$

where S and b are constants. S and b values for the various systems alongwith root mean square deviations of the experimental from the calculated values are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUE OF ΔV° , S , b AND σ FOR VARIOUS SYSTEMS

System	ΔV° ml mol ⁻¹	S	b	σ
NaPi + NaCl	17.20	-1.05	-1.435	0.11
TMA Pi + TMA Cl	17.62	-1.10	-0.80	0.10
TEA Pi + TEA Cl	18.10	-1.95	-0.43	0.06
TBA Pi + TBA Cl	19.25	-1.70	-0.24	0.10

If an assumption is made here (which derives support from Katz and Miller's work³), that the ionic strength contribution to ΔV is the same in all the systems and is equivalent to that observed in

sodium pivalate system, and on subtracting this value from the contributions made by the supporting electrolytes in tetraalkyl ammonium salt systems, we get residual volumes (ΔV_r) which may be attributed to the ion-pair association represented by equation (2). Now for one mole of protonation reaction,

$$\Delta V_M = \Delta V_s + (1 - \beta) \Delta V_d = \Delta V_d + \beta \Delta \Delta V \quad \dots (8)$$

where, $\Delta V_s = V_{PiH} + V_{TAA} + (V_{H+} + V_{TAA Pi})$

$$\Delta V_d = V_{PiH} + (V_{Pi'} + V_{H+})$$

and $\Delta \Delta V$ naturally means the change on dissociation of TAA Pi (a positive quantity). Substituting the value of β from equation (6) in equation (8) and rearranging.

$$\frac{1}{(\Delta V_M - \Delta V_d)} = \frac{1}{K_a \Delta \Delta V [TAA^+]} + \frac{1}{\Delta \Delta V} \quad \dots (9)$$

the denominator of the LHS is equated with the residual volumes defined above. Plots of LHS vs $\frac{1}{[TAA^+]}$ are shown in Fig. 1. Except for the extremal points where the residual volumes are very small and their reciprocals very large and sensitive, the plots approximate to straight lines and the intercepts obtained give the ΔV_r values which are of the order of about 5-20 ml mol⁻¹ for the three tetraalkyl ammonium systems. Here the absolute magnitude of these volumes of association is not being stressed as it very much depends upon the extrapolated values of ΔV° . But it is clear from Fig. 1 that the slopes decrease in the order TMA > TEA > TBA, i.e., $K_a \Delta \Delta V$ becomes larger in the same order, which is a reasonable trend. So here if not quantitatively but qualitatively, the ion pair association of tetraalkyl ammonium and carboxylate group (here pivalate) remains established.

References

1. J. KOMIYAMA, M. ANDO, Y. TAKEDA and T. IJIMA, *Polymer*, 1974, **15**, 468; *European Polymer Journal*, 1976, **12**, 201.
2. S. KATZ and J. MILLER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 1120; 1972, **76**, 2778.
3. M. SAKURAI, T. NAKAJIMA, T. KOMATSU and T. NAKAGAWA, *Chem. Lett.*, 1972, 355.
4. M. SAKURAI, T. KOMATSU and T. NAKAGAWA, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1975, **4**, 511.
5. A. BODANSKY and W. KAUFMANN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 177.